

EPSRC

Data management plan required?	Yes
RDM policy Link	No, however, https://epsrc.ukri.org/files/aboutus/standards/clarificationsofexpectationsresearchdatamanagement/
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	How raw data supporting publications will be accessed. How non-digital data will be stored and accessed. Restrictions on accessing data should be identified early on in process as subsequent restrictions would need substantial justification.
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	Meta data that adequately describes the research data should be made available within 12 months of the data being generated. Data that is not intended to be published, but that was produced after 1 st May 2015, should have associated metadata released online within 1 year of the date it was generated. Where there is no clear date of generation, the end date of the grant maybe used instead.
Time for long-term storage of data	Data should be securely kept for a minimum of 10 years - either from the date of the researcher's privileged access embargo or from the date the data was last accessed.
Costings	Costs associated with research funding can be requested in grant proposals as long as these costs are not double funded, and as long as the expenditure occurs before the end of the grant.
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	grants@epsrc.ac.uk
Comments	Applicants are not required to submit their DMP with their application although must acknowledge through a check box that they have a DMP in place.

Documents used: Clarifications of EPSRC expectations on research data management <https://epsrc.ukri.org/files/aboutus/standards/clarificationsofexpectationsresearchdatamanagement/>

Accessed: May 2018